

Special Issue - Feast of St. Francis Xavier

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PERCEPTUAL PROBLEMS
RELATED TO
PRESUPPOSITIONS

SOCIO-ECONOMIC
STATUS AND ACADEMIC
INTEREST

SOCIAL COMPETENCIES
OF SCHOOL
STUDENTS

JOB SATISFACTION
OF SCHOOL
TEACHERS

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AWARENESS AMONG
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CONSTRUCTIVIST
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PRACTICING
ALTERNATIVE
EDUCATION

WEB 2.0 TOOLS FOR
LEARNERS AT THE
HIGHER EDUCATION

St. Xavier's College of Education
(Autonomous)

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Dear Readers!

Yet another special issue emanates from the portals of St. Xavier's College of Education, Palayamkottai, Tamilnadu in order to celebrate the feast day of St. Francis Xavier SJ, the patron of our College. Francis Xavier, a Jesuit missionary from Spain reached at Goa, India in 1542 where he drove home the importance of Collegiate Education including literature, Philosophy and Theology through a seminary which catered to mainly seminarians and later to all from other sections. Known for his zeal, passion, sincerity and selflessness in his service to least in the society, he established himself among the Indians as the best teacher in communicating the 'Good News'. In fact he was considered to be an icon of an innovation and child-centred thoughts as he followed a unique way of attracting the children and elders for his sharing of his 'good news'. Reading the situation, he was able to transcend his academic superiority and became incarnated in the lives of the ordinary people of India.

In the context of today's educational scenario, one of the major impediments for a quality education is identified as the unwillingness of the teacher to reach the level of the students; this is because of the lack of in-depth reading of the profile of the students. Sometimes, even after knowing the background, teacher shirks his or her responsibility to modify the pedagogical strategy so that the students are motivated and attracted to learning. Leave alone the use of technology in the classroom transaction, the element of constantly accompanying the students in his or her academic search through the right pedagogy, appropriate reinforcement and comprehensive evaluation does not occur on the part of the teacher; this hinders the classroom climate and consequently the eagerness and attitude of the learners.

What do we have to do? A constant refreshment of the teaching fraternity in the techniques and pedagogy which would suit the needs and expectations of the learners becomes essential and indispensable. A low percentage of teachers seems to be exercising enthusiasm in updating themselves with modern trends whereas the maximum depend upon and wait for the initiatives of the Government education authorities to impose upon or organise the in-service programmes. A wonderful scheme titled as 'Samakra Shikshan' by Central Government is gaining momentum and able to collect the teachers across the table for a critical and evaluative thinking that leads to innovation and creative communication of content among the learners. Apart from the efforts of the Government, the teaching community has to be continually enthused for personal efforts of reading and reflecting on recent developments in their subjects which will enhance the teacher personality. With the advent of ICT, the student community has become well-informed and therefore teaching community too must be well-prepared in meeting the challenges from the classroom.

Dear Readers, we have good number of research papers and articles in this special issue; enjoy the reading and enhance your professional efficiency. I am sure, we will be able to mould a wonderful and fruitful younger generation with all our comprehensive efforts. Kindly send us your feedback and we will be grateful to you.

Thanking you in anticipation
Editorial Team

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A STUDY ON JOB SATISFACTION OF SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHERS

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ABSTRACT

The study was designed to examine some of the factors regarding job satisfaction of secondary school teachers working in government and private and urban and rural areas of Darjeeling district of West Bengal. The sample consists of 200 secondary school teachers selected randomly. The tool used for this study was 'Job satisfaction scale, Constructed and Standardized by (Mrs) Meera Dixit, (2013), Agra Research Laboratory Cell, Agra, Uttar Pradesh.

Keywords : Job satisfaction, Government and Private, Gender, Locality.

Introduction

Teaching is one of the noble occupations in the world or the kind contributor towards the society so a teacher has always been the strong spine of the society, his or her contribution towards the society or in an individual's life is forever. In an educational institute, one of the most important human resources is the teachers who not only work as a guide and a facilitator of knowledge but also teach the values and transform the inner being. To generate a worthy individual we also need an excellent teacher too. To be outstanding teacher knowledge isn't enough he or she should be satisfied and happy for what they are doing so they will carry their work forward. By examining their feelings or opinion of teachers, the psychologist has explained the observable fact of the task satisfaction. Teachers' job satisfaction has perhaps been investigated more and more, often in respect to teacher stress, job commitment, professional autonomy, school climate and so on. (Schuler, 1986). A variety of researches conducted in this field proves that it is important to have job satisfaction in the field of teaching so that the teachers can teach the student in-depth from various way as it is said that teachers are the nation builder who makes the normal person to a wise person who contributes to society for a better development.

Job satisfaction

The term "job satisfaction" refers to the feeling or the attitude towards their work, good attitude or positive feelings towards their work always lead to a success at what they do and bring satisfaction as a result whereas

negative and unfavorable attitude towards job lead to job dissatisfaction.

Bavendam (2000) teachers job satisfaction is much important of the hour because effective learning process of the students depends on the attitude of the teachers towards their job, so if they have job satisfaction then they can perform well in the classroom which leads the quality level in a high range and their maintenance rate becomes higher.

Judge, Thoresen, Bono, & Patton (2001) As job satisfaction is one of the most significant elements to quantify the employees feelings and attitude towards their work which can effect on the development of the organization and employees too.

Evans (1997) job satisfaction is an indefinite term because "satisfaction" can be "satisfactory" in some working situations but "satisfying" in other situations, it is difficult to clear or define the term satisfaction.

Need of the study

Teaching is a noble work as we all are aware of that but along with that it is a challenging profession too. As many teachers work at different levels, situations and need to work hard to educate in a best way as it is the

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responsibility of a teacher to develop their student so that they can become individually and socially useful. Apart from teaching they deal with many works in their daily life so to perform all the work smoothly every teacher needs to be emotionally and mentally fit so that they can be satisfied at what they do. As job satisfaction is one of the important factors in every working individual's life so that they can perform their laborious duty effectively so that their working condition should be made satisfactory. Therefore it is very much important of the hour to study about the job satisfaction of the teachers so that we can get wider pictures of the success and failures rates or a reason behind according to the factors.

Method and sampling frame

As the present study is concerned with the Secondary school teachers, survey method was adopted. Teachers from government and private, rural and urban were taken to constitute the population for the present study. The personal data sheet was also prepared to investigate the difference among the gender too. So to continue the investigation a simple random sampling technique was used with the 200 sample size.

Tools

Job satisfaction scale Standardized by Meera Dixit (2013) was used for the study. The scale consisted of 52 items. The score ranges from 52-260 having a 5 point (strongly agree, agree, undecided, disagree, strongly disagree) likert type scale. The scores of all the items were summed up for deriving an individual's job satisfaction score.

Objectives

1. To study the job satisfactiion of secondary school teachers in terms of selected background variables.

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant difference between urban and rural secondary school teachers regarding job satisfaction.
2. There is no significant difference between male and female secondary school teachers regarding job satisfaction.

3. There is no significant difference between government and private school secondary school teachers regarding job satisfaction.

Findings and Data Analysis

The data may be adequate, valid and reliable to any extent, it does not serve any worthwhile purpose unless it is carefully edited, systematically classified and tabulated, scientifically analysed, intelligently interpreted and nationally concluded.

The details of the analysis of data collected from the selected sample are given in the following tables.

Hypothesis 1 : There is no significant difference between Urban and Rural secondary school teachers regarding Job Satisfaction.

Table1
Job Satisfaction of Secondary School Teachers across locality

Job Satisfaction	Locality	Mean	SD	Calculated 't' value	Remark
	Urban	222.74	36.21	3.58	Significant at 0.01 level
	Rural	206.43	27.59		

The above table1 reveals that there is a significant difference between urban and rural secondary school teachers regarding job satisfaction at 0.01 level. Therefore the null hypothesis 'There is no significant difference between Urban and Rural secondary school teachers regarding Job Satisfaction is rejected.

Hypothesis 2 : There is no significant difference between male and female secondary school teachers regarding Job Satisfaction.

Table 2
Job Satisfaction of Secondary School Teachers in terms of gender

Job Satisfaction	Gender	Mean	SD	Calculated 't' value	Remark
	Male	226.83	28.2	5.95	Significant at 0.01
	Female	201.05	33.1		

The above table 2 shows that there is a significant difference between male and female secondary school teachers regarding job satisfaction at 0.01 level. Therefore the null hypothesis: ‘There is no significant difference between male and female secondary school teachers regarding Job Satisfaction’ is rejected.

Hypotheses 3

There is no significant difference between Government and Private secondary school teachers regarding Job Satisfaction.

higher job satisfaction of teachers on the areas like Gender, Management and Locality of secondary school teachers. Infrastructural facilities, administration, management should be improved and along with that focus should be in gender equality too so that equal opportunity and active participation can be made by both. Such study should be carried out on teachers in primary level school and college level too.

Table 3

Job Satisfaction of Secondary School Teachers in terms of school management

Job Satisfaction	Management	Mean	SD	Calculated ‘t’ value	Remark
	Private	214.93	34.14	0.15	NS
	Government	214.24	32.26		

The above table 3 shows that there is no significant difference between private and government secondary school teachers regarding Job Satisfaction therefore null hypothesis ‘There is no significance difference between Government and Private secondary school teachers regarding Job Satisfaction’ is accepted. .

Findings

From this study the investigator has drawn the following findings:

1. The study revealed that there is a significant difference between male and female secondary school teachers from Darjeeling district of West Bengal in their job satisfaction.
2. The study revealed that there is no significant difference between government and private secondary school teachers from Darjeeling district of West Bengal in their jobsatisfaction.
3. The study revealed that there is a significant difference between urban and rural secondary school teachers from Darjeeling district of West Bengal in their job satisfaction.

Conclusions and Suggestions

According to this study the investigator forwards some of the important suggestive measures to achieve the

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